

Building Executable Research Workflows for SSH Infrastructures: A WSO2-Based Orchestration Methodology within the H2IOSC Marketplace

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Abstract. Research infrastructures in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) offer a growing number of specialized digital services – from image repositories and handwritten text recognition engines to semantic annotation platforms and digital publishing systems. However, researchers who need to combine multiple services into coherent research workflows typically face the burden of manually transferring data between systems, adapting output formats, and managing authentication across platforms. This paper presents a methodology for building executable, orchestrated research workflows within the H2IOSC Marketplace, using WSO2 Micro Integrator as the orchestration engine. The methodology builds on the orchestration framework that CNR-ILIESI and OPERAS-IT have designed and documented since March 2023 as the reference model for cross-infrastructure service integration within H2IOSC. We describe the complete lifecycle of an orchestrated workflow: from service registration and API specification, through pipeline design and implementation using WSO2 artifacts (APIs, sequences, mediators, message stores, and message processors), to packaging, deployment, and publication in the Marketplace. We detail the architectural patterns required for robust cross-infrastructure orchestration, including asynchronous polling for long-running services, payload transformation between heterogeneous APIs, XSLT-based format conversion, and error handling in distributed environments. The methodology is grounded in the orchestration framework conceived by OPERAS-IT within the H2IOSC project, which distinguishes between orchestration (remote, cross-infrastructure service coordination) and composition (local, intra-infrastructure service organization). We provide reusable design patterns and implementation guidelines that can be adopted by other federated research infrastructure projects facing similar integration challenges. The methodology applies to both WSO2 Micro Integrator (for workflow execution) and WSO2 API Manager (for API governance and lifecycle management), covering the complete WSO2 integration stack as deployed within the H2IOSC Marketplace architecture.

Keywords: workflow orchestration, WSO2 Micro Integrator, research infrastructure, H2IOSC, OPERAS, OPERAS-IT, API integration, pipeline methodology, SSH, Social Sciences and Humanities, digital humanities, service integration, asynchronous orchestration, FAIR, WSO2 API Manager, PNRR

1. Introduction

1.1 The Workflows in SSH Research

Modern research in the Social Sciences and Humanities increasingly relies on digital tools and services distributed across multiple platforms and infrastructures. A typical Digital Humanities research workflow might involve: accessing high-resolution manuscript images from a cultural heritage repository; processing them through a Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) service; enriching the resulting transcription with semantic annotations; and publishing the final result as a structured digital edition. Each of these steps is typically provided by a different institution, accessed through a different interface, and produces output in a different format.

In current practice, researchers must perform these integration tasks manually: downloading outputs, reformatting data, uploading to the next service, monitoring progress, and handling errors. This manual process is time-consuming, error-prone, and non-reproducible. It also creates a significant barrier to entry for researchers who lack technical expertise in API programming and data transformation.

1.2 The OPERAS-IT Orchestration Framework

The orchestration framework developed by OPERAS-IT within the H2IOSC project addresses this challenge by providing a systematic approach to combining distributed services into executable, automated workflows. The framework, first conceived in April 2023 and progressively formalized through a series of technical documents [1, 2, 3, 4], introduces a clear separation between the Marketplace (which orchestrates) and the infrastructure services (which execute), as well as a formal distinction between orchestration and composition [4].

Figure 1 - OPERAS-IT: Intellectual Authorship of Service Orchestration within H2IOSC. Timeline from initial prototypal definition (April 2023) to operational deployment (March 2026). All documents were produced by OPERAS-IT / CNR-ILIESI.

The present paper focuses on the practical methodology for building orchestrated workflows within this framework. While the conceptual foundations are described in [3] and the metadata interoperability layer in [5], this paper addresses the service-level orchestration layer: how

individual infrastructure services are registered, how workflows are designed and implemented, and how they are deployed and executed through the Marketplace.

1.3 Scope and Structure

This paper presents a general methodology, not a single case study. The design patterns and implementation techniques described here are intended to be reusable across different workflow scenarios and infrastructure configurations. Specific case studies demonstrating the application of this methodology to concrete research workflows are presented in companion publications.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses related work on workflow orchestration in research contexts. Section 3 describes the architectural foundations. Section 4 presents the workflow lifecycle. Section 5 details the implementation patterns. Section 6 discusses the design patterns for robust orchestration. Section 7 addresses deployment and publication. Section 8 concludes.

2. Related Work

2.1 Workflow Systems in Digital Humanities

The Digital Humanities community has developed several approaches to workflow management. Galaxy, originally designed for bioinformatics, has been adapted for text analysis workflows. Taverna and its successor Apache Taverna provided a graphical workflow design environment, but development has ceased. CLARIN's WebLicht offers a web-based pipeline for natural language processing tools, but is limited to the CLARIN infrastructure ecosystem. More recently, Jupyter Notebooks have become a de facto standard for documenting and sharing research workflows, but they require programming skills and do not provide true service orchestration – they execute code locally rather than coordinating remote services.

2.2 Service Orchestration in Research Infrastructures

At the infrastructure level, the EOSC-Hub project developed a PaaS orchestration framework based on TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications) [6], designed for deploying and managing cloud services at scale. While powerful, TOSCA-based orchestration targets infrastructure provisioning rather than research workflow coordination, and its complexity places it beyond the reach of most SSH research teams.

The SSHOC project adopted a simpler approach, focusing on metadata interoperability through API-based data exchange rather than service orchestration. The SSH Open Marketplace catalogues tools and services but does not orchestrate their execution.

2.3 WSO2 as an Integration Platform

WSO2 is an open-source integration platform widely adopted in enterprise environments for API management and service integration. WSO2 Micro Integrator (MI), the lightweight integration runtime, provides a comprehensive set of mediators (processing units) based on the Apache Synapse mediation framework, supporting message transformation, protocol switching, and

complex integration patterns. While well-established in enterprise contexts, its application to research infrastructure orchestration has not been previously documented in the literature.

2.4 Positioning of This Work

This paper addresses a gap between the research workflow systems (which are often limited to single-platform execution) and enterprise integration platforms (which are not designed for research contexts). By applying WSO2 Micro Integrator within the OPERAS-IT orchestration framework, we demonstrate that enterprise-grade service orchestration can be made accessible to federated research infrastructures without requiring cloud-scale deployments or specialized infrastructure expertise.

3. Architectural Foundations

3.1 The Orchestration Model

The H2IOSC orchestration model, as defined in [3, 4], establishes the following architectural principles:

Separation of orchestration and execution. The Marketplace, operating through WSO2 Micro Integrator, coordinates the workflow by invoking remote services in sequence. It never executes computational tasks directly. Each service runs on its own infrastructure, maintained by its respective provider.

Orchestration vs. composition. When the Marketplace coordinates services across infrastructure boundaries (remote invocation, network protocols, asynchronous handling), we speak of orchestration. When services are combined within a single platform (local invocation, synchronous execution), we speak of composition. A composed workflow within one infrastructure can be exposed as a meta-service and participate in broader orchestration scenarios.

Figure 2 – Integration patterns supported by the WSO2 platform. The H2IOSC Marketplace methodology described in this paper targets orchestration (centre), where WSO2 Micro Integrator coordinates remote services in sequence. Composition (left), where services are managed within a single API Manager instance, corresponds to intra-infrastructure platforms. The methodology does not address choreography (right).

Runtime parameterization. All workflow parameters (service endpoints, credentials, input data) are provided at runtime through the initial JSON request. No URLs, credentials, or configuration values are hardcoded in the workflow definition. This ensures that the same workflow can be executed against different service instances without modification.

It is worth noting that the orchestration model described here operates at a different architectural level than composition environments deployed within individual infrastructures. For example, DARIAH-IT’s AEON platform [12] enables workflow creation using WSO2, but requires that all participating services be registered and deployed within the AEON instance. The methodology presented in this paper targets the Marketplace level of the entire H2IOSC project, where services from any infrastructure – including those composed within platforms such as AEON – can be orchestrated without requiring their redeployment. Both the WSO2 API Manager (for API governance) and WSO2 Micro Integrator (for workflow execution) are covered by this methodology, as both components are deployed within the H2IOSC Marketplace architecture.

3.2 Component Architecture

The orchestration layer comprises three main components:

WSO2 API Manager manages the API lifecycle: registration, versioning, access control, throttling, and monitoring. Each infrastructure service that participates in orchestration is registered as a managed API with its OpenAPI/YAML specification.

WSO2 Micro Integrator executes the workflow logic. A workflow is defined as a set of WSO2 artifacts: an API (the entry point), one or more sequences (the processing steps), mediators (individual operations within sequences), and optionally message stores and processors (for asynchronous patterns).

The Marketplace back-office provides the user interface for workflow publication, configuration, and triggering. It interacts with WSO2 through its management APIs.

3.3 Service Requirements

For a service to participate in orchestrated workflows, it must satisfy the following minimum requirements:

1. **API accessibility.** The service must expose a REST or SOAP API that can be invoked programmatically over HTTP/HTTPS.
2. **Documented interface.** The API must be documented with an OpenAPI/YAML specification or equivalent.
3. **Standard authentication.** The service must use a standard authentication mechanism (API key, Bearer token, Basic auth, OAuth 2.0).
4. **Structured output.** The service must produce output in a machine-parseable format (JSON, XML, or a domain-specific format such as ALTO XML or TEI XML).

Services that meet these requirements can be integrated into orchestrated workflows without any modification to the service itself. The orchestrator adapts to the service, not the other way around.

4. Workflow Lifecycle

The lifecycle of an orchestrated workflow in the H2IOSC Marketplace follows six phases.

H2IOSC Orchestrated Workflow Lifecycle: 6-Phase Methodology

Figure 3 - Workflow lifecycle

4.1 Phase 1: Service Registration

Services that participate in Marketplace-published workflows fall into two categories. Services owned by the participating infrastructures, or otherwise intended for discovery and reuse by the research community, are registered in the Marketplace catalogue: registration involves describing the service's functionality, input/output formats, and access requirements; providing the OpenAPI/YAML specification; configuring authentication parameters; and testing the API endpoints for availability and conformance. External services – those maintained by third parties and accessed only as dependencies of specific workflows – do not require catalogue registration: they are referenced at runtime through their URL and API credentials, provided as parameters in the workflow invocation. This flexibility allows workflows to integrate any API-accessible service, including resources hosted outside the H2IOSC ecosystem, as demonstrated in the IIIF-eScriptorium-TEI Publisher workflow presented in [13].

The service description follows the H2IOSC data model [7], which supports eight resource types (tool, dataset, publication, project, service, terminology_resource, learning_resource, workflow) with type-specific properties, multilingual metadata, and structured identity management.

4.2 Phase 2: Workflow Design

Workflow design involves defining the sequence of service invocations, the data transformations between services, and the error handling strategy. The design is guided by the following considerations:

Registration boundary. Which services are catalogued in the Marketplace (and thus discoverable and reusable) and which are referenced as external dependencies?

Service ordering. Which services must be called in which order? What are the data dependencies between services?

Format compatibility. Does the output of service A match the expected input of service B? If not, what transformation is needed?

Synchronicity. Does each service respond synchronously (result available immediately) or asynchronously (result available after processing, requiring polling)?

Error scenarios. What happens if a service is unavailable, returns an error, or times out? Should the workflow retry, skip, or abort?

The design phase produces a workflow specification document that describes the complete flow, including all transformation and error handling logic.

4.3 Phase 3: Implementation

The workflow is implemented as a set of WSO2 Micro Integrator artifacts using the WSO2 plugin for Visual Studio Code. The implementation translates the workflow design into executable integration logic. The artifacts are detailed in Section 5.

4.4 Phase 4: Packaging

The implemented artifacts are compiled into a .car (Carbon Application Archive) file using the WSO2 build tools. The .car file is a self-contained, deployable unit that includes all APIs, sequences, mediators, message stores, processors, and transformation resources (XSLT stylesheets, JSON schemas) required by the workflow.

4.5 Phase 5: Deployment and Testing

The .car file is deployed to the WSO2 Micro Integrator instance managed by the Marketplace. Deployment involves: uploading the .car through the Marketplace back-office or the WSO2 management API; verifying that all service endpoints are reachable; executing test runs with known inputs and validating outputs; and monitoring performance and error rates.

4.6 Phase 6: Publication

Once tested, the workflow is published in the Marketplace catalogue as a new item of type “workflow.” The catalogue entry includes: the workflow description (multilingual); the input parameters specification; the expected output format; the list of constituent services (with links to their catalogue entries); and the pipeline configuration for execution.

Published workflows appear alongside individual services in the Marketplace catalogue and can be discovered, explored, and triggered by researchers through the Marketplace interface.

5. Implementation Artifacts

5.1 API Definition

Each workflow is exposed as a WSO2 API – an HTTP endpoint that receives the initial request and returns the final result. The API definition specifies: the URL context path; the accepted HTTP methods (typically POST for workflow triggering); the expected request payload (JSON, containing all runtime parameters); and the response format.

The API is defined in an XML artifact following the Apache Synapse configuration syntax, or visually through the WSO2 plugin’s graphical editor.

Starting from version 4.3.0 (July 2024), the WSO2 MI extension for VS Code includes MI Copilot, an AI-powered assistant that generates integration artifacts from natural language descriptions or uploaded OpenAPI specifications [11]. Developers can describe their orchestration scenario in plain text (e.g., “create a pipeline that calls an HTR service, polls for completion, transforms the output from ALTO XML to TEI, and publishes it to a REST endpoint”) and MI Copilot generates the corresponding API definition, sequences, and mediator configurations. While the generated artifacts typically require manual refinement – particularly for complex patterns such as multi-phase asynchronous polling – MI Copilot significantly reduces the initial scaffolding effort and lowers the learning curve for developers unfamiliar with the Apache Synapse configuration syntax.

5.2 Sequences

Sequences are the core processing units of a workflow. A sequence is an ordered list of mediators that process the message in series. Typical sequences in a workflow include:

Main sequence (inSequence): receives the initial request, extracts parameters, and initiates the first service call.

Service-specific sequences: for each constituent service, a sequence that constructs the appropriate API call, handles the response, and prepares the input for the next service.

Transform sequences: sequences dedicated to data format conversion between services (e.g., converting ALTO XML output to TEI XML input).

Error sequences (faultSequence): sequences that handle errors at each stage, logging the error, notifying the user, and performing cleanup if necessary.

5.3 Mediators

Mediators are the individual processing steps within sequences. The most commonly used mediators in research workflow orchestration include:

PayloadFactory mediator: constructs or transforms the message payload. Used to build API request bodies from workflow parameters and to extract relevant fields from service responses.

Call mediator: invokes an external service endpoint and waits for the response. Used for synchronous service calls.

Filter mediator: implements conditional logic based on message content. Used for branching (e.g., checking whether a service returned a success or error status).

Property mediator: sets or retrieves properties on the message context. Used for passing data between mediators and sequences.

XSLT mediator: applies an XSLT stylesheet to transform XML content. Used for converting between domain-specific XML formats (e.g., ALTO XML to TEI XML).

Log mediator: logs message content for debugging and monitoring purposes.

Store mediator: stores the current message in a message store for deferred processing. Used in asynchronous polling patterns.

5.4 Message Stores and Processors

For services that process requests asynchronously (i.e., the result is not available immediately but only after a processing period), WSO2 provides message stores and message processors:

In-Memory Message Store: temporarily holds messages that are waiting for asynchronous processing to complete.

Sampling Message Processor: periodically retrieves messages from the store and re-processes them. In the context of orchestration, this is used to implement polling: the processor periodically

checks whether the asynchronous service has completed processing and, if so, retrieves the result and proceeds with the workflow.

This pattern is essential for orchestrating services such as HTR engines or batch processing systems, which may take minutes or hours to complete.

5.5 XSLT Transformations

Many research services produce output in domain-specific XML formats that do not directly match the input requirements of downstream services. XSLT (Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformations) provides a powerful, standards-based mechanism for converting between XML formats.

In the context of research workflow orchestration, typical XSLT transformations include:

ALTO XML to TEI: converting the output of OCR/HTR services (which produce ALTO XML with page layout and text content) into TEI P5 format (which structures the text for scholarly editing and publishing). This transformation must map ALTO's spatial model (pages, text blocks, text lines, strings with coordinate attributes) to TEI's facsimile model (surfaces, zones with coordinate attributes) while preserving the link between transcribed text and its position on the source image.

Custom metadata mapping: converting service-specific metadata formats into the H2IOSC data model for catalogue integration.

The XSLT stylesheets are packaged as resources within the .car file and referenced by the XSLT mediator in the workflow sequences.

6. Design Patterns for Robust Orchestration

6.1 Asynchronous Polling Pattern

Many research services – particularly those involving computationally intensive tasks such as HTR, image segmentation, or natural language processing – operate asynchronously: the initial API call triggers the processing and returns immediately with a job identifier or status URL; the actual result becomes available only after the processing completes.

The asynchronous polling pattern addresses this using WS02's message infrastructure:

1. The workflow calls the service's trigger endpoint.
2. Instead of waiting, it stores the current message context (including the job identifier) in an in-memory message store.
3. A sampling message processor periodically retrieves messages from the store.
4. For each message, it calls the service's status endpoint to check whether processing is complete.
5. If processing is still in progress, the message is returned to the store for later re-checking.
6. If processing is complete, the message proceeds to the next stage of the workflow.

This pattern can be chained for workflows involving multiple asynchronous services. The polling interval and maximum retry count are configurable per service, allowing the orchestrator to adapt to services with different processing times.

6.2 Multi-Phase Polling

Some services involve multiple sequential processing phases, each of which must complete before the next can begin. For example, an HTR service might require: document import (asynchronous), layout segmentation (asynchronous), text recognition (asynchronous), and result export (asynchronous).

The multi-phase polling pattern extends the basic polling pattern by maintaining a phase indicator in the message context. The sampling processor checks the status of the current phase and, upon completion, triggers the next phase before returning the message to the store for monitoring.

This pattern avoids the need for separate message stores per phase and allows the entire multi-phase processing to be managed by a single processor.

6.3 Payload Transformation Chain

When services in a workflow use different data formats, the orchestrator must transform the output of each service into the format expected by the next. The payload transformation chain pattern encapsulates each transformation in a dedicated sequence, allowing transformations to be reused across different workflows.

For example, a “transform-alto-to-tei” sequence can be shared between any workflow that involves an OCR/HTR service producing ALTO XML followed by a TEI-based service. This promotes modularity and reduces duplication.

6.4 Runtime Parameterization Pattern

To ensure that workflows are reusable across different environments and service instances, all configuration values must be provided at runtime rather than hardcoded in the workflow artifacts. The runtime parameterization pattern uses the initial JSON request payload to supply: service endpoint URLs; authentication credentials (API keys, Bearer tokens); input data (document URLs, manifest URIs); and processing parameters (model selection, output format preferences).

The PayloadFactory mediator extracts these values from the initial request and injects them into subsequent service calls using Property mediators. This means that the same .car file can be deployed in different environments (development, staging, production) and used with different service providers without modification.

6.5 Error Propagation and Recovery

Distributed workflows are inherently susceptible to network failures, service unavailability, and unexpected responses. The error propagation pattern ensures that errors are captured, logged, and communicated to the user at each stage:

Service-level error handling: each service call is wrapped in a try-catch pattern using the `faultSequence`. If a service returns an error, the fault sequence logs the error with contextual information (which service, which phase, what input was provided) and either retries the call or aborts the workflow with an informative error message.

Timeout management: each service call includes a configurable timeout. If a service does not respond within the timeout period, the orchestrator treats it as an error and follows the fault sequence.

Partial result handling: for workflows involving independent parallel branches (future extension), the error in one branch does not necessarily abort the entire workflow. Partial results from successful branches can be returned to the user.

7. Deployment and Publication

7.1 Building the .car File

The workflow artifacts are compiled into a `.car` file using the WSO2 build tools integrated in the Visual Studio Code plugin. The build process validates the XML syntax of all artifacts, resolves internal references between sequences and mediators, packages all resources (XSLT stylesheets, JSON schemas, WSDL files) into the archive, and produces a self-contained deployable unit.

7.2 Deploying to WSO2 Micro Integrator

The `.car` file is deployed to the WSO2 Micro Integrator instance through the Marketplace back-office. The deployment process uploads the archive, extracts and registers all contained artifacts, activates the API endpoint, and verifies that the workflow responds to test requests.

7.3 Publishing in the Marketplace Catalogue

Once deployed, the workflow is registered in the Marketplace catalogue as an item of type “workflow.” The catalogue entry follows the H2IOSC data model [7] and includes: multilingual name and description; the list of constituent services (linked to their own catalogue entries); input parameters specification; expected output format and structure; and access requirements and authentication method.

The published workflow is discoverable through the Marketplace search interface and can be triggered by authorized users. The Marketplace provides a user-facing form that collects the required input parameters and submits them to the WSO2 API endpoint, abstracting the technical complexity from the end user. Published workflows will be accessible through the H2IOSC Marketplace at <https://marketplace.h2iosc.cnr.it>.

7.4 Versioning and Updates

Workflows evolve as constituent services change their APIs or as new processing capabilities become available. The versioning strategy follows standard API versioning practices: the API context path includes a version identifier (e.g., /v1/pipeline-name); new versions are deployed alongside existing ones; users can choose which version to execute; and deprecated versions are maintained for a transition period before removal.

8. Reusability and Generalization

8.1 Applicability Beyond H2IOSC

The methodology presented in this paper is not specific to the H2IOSC project or its constituent infrastructures. Any federated research project that requires cross-service integration can adopt the same approach, provided that: the participating services expose REST or SOAP APIs; a WSO2 Micro Integrator instance is available (WSO2 MI is open-source and can run on modest hardware); and the workflow designer has access to the API documentation of the constituent services.

8.2 Relationship to EOSC and SSHOC

The H2IOSC Marketplace is designed to be interoperable with the EOSC and SSHOC ecosystems at the metadata level (through OAI-PMH harvesting). At the service level, workflows built using the methodology described in this paper can integrate services from any infrastructure, including those catalogued in the EOSC or SSHOC marketplaces, provided they satisfy the service requirements described in Section 3.3.

8.3 Limitations

The current methodology has several limitations. First, all workflows are currently sequential (each service is called after the previous one completes). Parallel execution of independent workflow branches is architecturally possible with WSO2 MI but has not yet been implemented. Second, the methodology assumes that all services are API-accessible. Services that require manual interaction (e.g., web-based annotation tools) cannot be integrated into fully automated workflows. Third, the asynchronous polling pattern introduces latency, as the polling interval must balance responsiveness against API rate limiting.

9. Conclusions and Future Work

This paper has presented a methodology for building executable, orchestrated research workflows within the H2IOSC Marketplace using WSO2 Micro Integrator. The methodology covers the complete workflow lifecycle from service registration through design, implementation, packaging, deployment, and publication.

The key contributions are:

1. A systematic methodology for translating research workflows into executable WSO2 Micro Integrator artifacts, applicable to any combination of API-accessible services.
2. A set of reusable design patterns for robust cross-infrastructure orchestration, including asynchronous polling, multi-phase polling, payload transformation chains, runtime parameterization, and error propagation.
3. Integration with the OPERAS-IT orchestration framework [3, 4], demonstrating how the conceptual distinction between orchestration and composition translates into concrete implementation choices.

The methodology, together with the orchestration framework in which it is grounded, was conceived and developed by OPERAS-IT / CNR-ILIESI within the H2IOSC project. Its application to concrete research workflows in the Digital Humanities domain is demonstrated in companion case study publications.

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